

HYPOLIPEDMIC EFFECT OF THE COMBINATION OF NATURAL ASIMAGES AGAINST DIABETES

Yuldashev X.E ¹, Negmatova M.F ², Kucharova M.F ³

Qurbonova G.Q ⁴, Narzullaeva G.Q ⁵

Termez branch of Tashkent medical academy, Termez

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590073>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th May 2022

Accepted: 14th May 2022

Online: 27th May 2022

KEY WORDS

herbal medicines,
hypocholesterolemic,
hyperlipidemia, treatment,
phytodiabetol, diabetes.

ABSTRACT

Efficacy of hypolipidemic and hypocholesterolemic effect of galega officinalis i plant extract. This article discusses the structure of the galega plant.

The relevance of the topic. Nowadays several studies are underway on the efficacy of hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effect of Galega officinalis I plant extract. However, the hypolipidemic and hypocholesterolemic effects of the plant are poorly understood. Taking that into account, for the first time the hypolipidemic and hypocholesterolemic properties of this plant in different models of diabetes were studied in comparison with α -lipoic acid.

Medical and social significance of diabetes severe_complications of the disease are explained by increasing of numbers of disabilities and death. Therefore, it is important to study the pharmacological properties of local herbal medicines for the treatment of hyperlipidemia and hypercholesterolemia. Medicinal goat extract reduces glucose concentration glycated hemoglobin total cholesterol increases the amount of oxides in high

density lipoproteins. In practice, the comparison of Galega officinalis I plant extract with α -lipoic acid has been studied. The disclosure of the mechanisms of hypoglycemic action is of particular importance in the implementation of pre-hospital research and application in medicine.

The purpose of the research. To study the hypolipidemic effect on animals and to to apply it in medical practice.

The method and material of the research. In our study, 15 healthy female rabbits with a body weight of 2,4 – 3,8 kg were selected to determine the effect of experimental rabbits on serum lipid spectra in the dithizone model of diabetes. The rabbits were divided into 5 groups of three in each. Once a day for 30 days they were injected into the ear vein with dissolved in ammonia water at a dose of 25 mg/kg the effect of phytodiabetol at

doses of 6 and 69 mg/kg was studied in the mild form of diathesis diabetes.

The results of the research: It is known that in type 1 diabetes, the process of lipolysis increases and the amount of triglycerides in the serum increases. In type 2 diabetes, obesity develops. Therefore, subsequent experiments have studied the effect of phytodiabetol on serum lipids in diabetic diabetes. In the background of diabetes mellitus, the amount of total lipids in the serum increased from $9,3 \pm 0,2$ g/l to $17,0 \pm 0,6$ g/l (82,8%; $P < 0,001$), triglycerides from $2,15 \pm 0,14$ mmol/l to $3,47 \pm 0,21$ mmol/l (61,4%; $P < 0,001$), cholesterol from $1,30 \pm 0,13$ mmol/l to $8,41 \pm 0,19$ mmol/l (64,6%; $P < 0,00001$), β - lipoproteins from $2,32 \pm 0,17$ g/l to $2,84 \pm 0,11$ g/l (22,4%; $P < 0,05$) compared to control group (1st table). The

amount of cholesterol and triglycerides in the blood were significantly reduced by 44,8 and 47 % and 47,3% and 52,5%, compared to the control group at the doses studied under the influence of phytopreparation, the comparative drug under the influence of α - lipoic acid reduced the amount of cholesterol in the blood by 54,6% respectively, triglycerides were lower than intact. It was also found that β - lipoproteins did not lag behind α - lipoic acid in its effect on reducing the amount of lipoproteins in the blood (13,7% and 18,7%).

Effects of the medicinal plant Galega officinalis I on the spectrum of lipids in the serum of experimental rabbits during treatment ($n=3, M \pm m$)

Groups	Lipid spectrum indicator		
	Cholesterol, mmol/l	Triglycerides mmol/l	β lipoproteins g/l
Intact	$1,30 \pm 0,13$ ^^	$2,15 \pm 0,14$ ^^	$2,32 \pm 0,17$ ^^
Diabetes mellitus + distilled water	$8,41 \pm 0,19$ ^	$3,47 \pm 0,21$ ^	$2,84 \pm 0,11$ ^
Diabetes mellitus + α - lipoic acid	$3,82 \pm 0,33$ ^^^	$1,64 \pm 0,12$ ^^^	$2,25 \pm 0,23$ ^^
Diabetes mellitus + Galega officinalis I 1,6 mg/kg	$4,64 \pm 0,25$ ^^^	$1,83 \pm 0,15$ ^^^	$2,45 \pm 0,22$ ^^
Diabetes mellitus + Galega officinalis I 1,60 mg/kg	$4,45 \pm 0,12$ ^^^	$1,65 \pm 0,21$ ^^	$2,31 \pm 0,05$ ^^

Comment^Level of reliability of the results obtained in intact

animals ($R < 0,05$) ^^Level of reliability in relation to the results obtained from control animals ($R < 0,05$)

When treated with the medicinal plant Galega officinalis I, the total lipid content increased by 40% ($10,2 \pm 0,5$ g/l; $R < 0,01$) 42,3% ($9,8 \pm 0,4$ g/l; $R < 0,01$) compared to the control group at doses 6 and 60 mg/kg

decreased significantly and did not differ from the intact indicators. Under the influence of comparative hypolipidemik drug (α - lipoic acid) its content decreased by 45,3% ($9,3 \pm 0,7$ g/l; $R < 0,01$).

Conclusion: In our study, the dithizone model of diabetes was characterized by a reliable increase in total lipid levels by $17,0 \pm 0,6$ g/l; ($R < 0,001$) times, triglycerides 1,61 times, cholesterol 6,47 times and β -

lipoproteins 1,22 times. The medicinal plant *Galega officinalis* L has hypolipidemic, hypotriglyceridemic and hypocholesterolemic properties.

But the hypocholesterolemic activity of the medicinal plant *Galega officinalis* L was several times lower than the activity of α -lipoic acid. It is clear that the medicinal plant *Galega officinalis* L has a positive effect on the secretion of insulin from pancreas, improves the metabolism of fats in the

tissues. Based on the above, it can be concluded that the medicinal plant *Galega officinalis* L can be recommended in the prevention and treatment of disorders of fat metabolism in type 2 diabetes.

The results show that the medicinal plant *Galega officinalis* L can be recommended for the treatment of hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes, as well as for the correction of hypolipidemia and hypercholesterolemia.

References:

1. Abdullayevich, B. E., & Uchqun o'g'li, B. S. (2021). TRANSITIONAL FEATURES OF ACUTE HERPETIC STOMATITIS IN CHILDREN AND MODERN APPROACHES TO TREATMENT. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 1(1), 1-3.
2. Ugli, B. S. U., & Bekchanovich, K. Y. (2020). CLASSIFICATION OF VITAMINS AND DISEASE SYNDROME. *Science and Education*, 1(1).
3. Madiyev Rustam Zoirovich, Boboyorov Sardor Uchqun o'g'li, & Abdullaeva Dilnoza Ergashevna. (2021). EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOVIDEOLAPAROSCOPIC TECHNOLOGY IN THE TREATMENT AND EARLY PREVENTION OF INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(7), 68-73. Retrieved from <https://www.scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrds/article/view/1067>
4. Sulstonov, R. K., Sodiqova, Z. S., & o'g'li, B. S. U. (2021). Dynamics of Fat Cells of the Bronchial Tree Mucosa in Postnatal Ontogenesis. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES*, 2(4), 182-184. <https://doi.org/10.47494/cajms.v2i4.271>
5. GI Shaykhova, JB Khayitov, Achilov Dilshod Dilmurodovich, *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication* 1 (6), 109-111, 2021
6. Dilmurodovich, A. D., Bahodirovich, G. Y., Dustqobilovich, A. K., & Uchqun o'g'li, B. S. (2021). Comparative Features of Breast Cancer in Patients with and Non-Suffering with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 12, 68-70. Retrieved from <http://ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/265>